

AUTOMATIC EXPERIMENTAL LABORATORY FOR CHECKING THE QUALITY OF WORKPIECES

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ABSTRACT: In recent years, experimental laboratories have begun to gain momentum in terms of industrial development, being increasingly used and present in the activities carried out in the prototyping of production lines. The automated quality verification process of parts processed on machine tools has over time gained significant importance in the validation of the final product. The paper presents an experimental stand for verifying the quality of processed parts. The stand checks the parts using an optical sensor, a capacitive sensor, an inductive sensor and a pneumatic cylinder for checking the depth of the parts. At the same time, the paper presents the way in which the part validation activity is carried out and the operating mode of the system.

KEYWORDS: Industrial Robots, Robotic Cell, Robotics Laboratory, Automation

1 INTRODUCTION

In Robotics education, especially in e-learning environments in higher education, it is very important to use laboratories that allow us to practice the acquired knowledge and to observe the real errors or problems that can appear in a real system but do not exist in simulated or virtual laboratories. (Chaos 2013), (Gomes 2009), (de la Torre 2011). Technical fields, like Mechanical Engineering and Electrical Engineering, need laboratory exercises. These exercises mean physical experiments with real equipment. (Potkonjak 2010).

A significant challenge facing the effort to bring robots into the daily lives of nontechnical users is their limited and inflexible behavioral repertoire. Expert roboticists can program new policies and skills within specialized domains such as manufacturing and lab experimentation. (Osentoski 2012), (Argall 2009). Robotics is a field that focuses on the development and study of robots, encompassing the modeling, design, and manufacturing of robotic systems. Industrial robots are extensively employed in the automotive and electronics industries, as well as in other fields. In today's manufacturing industry, vision-guided robotic picking systems play a vital role in automating various tasks. However, achieving rapid

changeover and adaptability for diverse workpiece types has remained a significant challenge.

In this paper, the aim is to program an experimental stand for feeding a conveyor belt and checking the quality of the parts introduced into the workspace.

2 THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS AND EXPERIMENTAL STAND

In order to carry out the proposed experiment, a Bosch Rexroth workbench was used. The functional stand used is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 Bosch Rexroth experimental stand

The stand consists of the following elements:

- feed belt;

- two magazines for feeding the stand with workpieces;
- optical sensors;
- inductive sensor;
- pneumatic cylinder;
- capacitive sensor.

These elements can be seen in Figure 2. From left to right, the sensors can be identified as optic sensor, inductive sensor, pneumatic cylinder and capacitive sensor. They can be flexibly modified on any side of the conveyor belt to achieve different projects.

Fig 2. Equipment presentation

The stand is controlled from the control panel shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3 Stand control panel

The elements of the panel are as follows as numbered in figure 2:

1. Emergency button;
2. Authorization level key;
3. 2 x 15 configurable buttons;
4. Feed/spindle change;
5. Button On/Off;
6. Profibus connector, emergency stop circuit and power supply.

It has two modes of use, the manual one in which each element of the stand is manipulated individually using the buttons on the control panel, and the automatic one in which it works according to a pre-established work program.

To feed the conveyor belt, a series of parts were designed as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4 Design of parts (a) Isometric projection (b) Dimensions of parts (c) and (d) different depths of parts.

The parts used are made of various metal and plastic materials made through milling or 3D printing processes. These manufactured parts are shown in Figure 5.

Fig 5. The workpieces used in the experimental stand.

3 EXPERIMENTAL STAND WORKING METHOD

As an initial step, the stand will feed the conveyor belt with the parts to be checked through the two magazines it is equipped with. The two magazines are shown in figure 6.

Fig 6. Conveyor belt feed magazines

In the next step, the parts will pass through inductive and capacitive sensors to verify the composition of the workpieces, but also through the feeler to verify the depth of the parts passing through the workspace. This process is shown in figure 7.

Fig 7. Parts verification process.

After checking the parts, they will be transported to the final optical sensor to determine their position on the conveyor belt. This sensor is shown in figure 8.

Fig. 8 Optical sensor for detecting the position of parts.

If the part complies with the verification requirements of the experimental stand, it will be transported to the next processing element of the system. Otherwise, it will be sent back to the pneumatic cylinder which will guide the non-compliant part out of the conveyor belt. The part will be evacuated to a storage space to be later manually retrieved from the stand. This evacuation process of the part is shown in figure 9.

Fig 9. The storage space where non-conforming parts are guided.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The work is the subject of the presentation of an experimental laboratory stand for transporting and checking the quality of parts. In carrying out the work, Bosch Rexroth equipment was used, which contained a conveyor belt, inductive and capacitive sensors, optical sensors and a pneumatic cylinder.

For the experimental part of the project, pieces of metal and plastic materials obtained through milling and 3D printing processes were made. The stand feeds the conveyor belt, checks the parts fed using sensors and finally validates the conformity of the parts. If the parts tested do not meet the conformity requirements, they will be evacuated from the stand. The stand is part of an ensemble of functional stands and is used for educational purposes. Depending on the verification

requirements, it can be adapted to different varieties of projects.

REFERENCES

Chaos, D., Chacón, J., Lopez-Orozco, J. A., & Dormido, S. (2013). Virtual and remote robotic laboratory using EJS, MATLAB and LabVIEW. *Sensors*, 13(2), 2595-2612.

Gomes, L., & Bogosyan, S. (2009). Current trends in remote laboratories. *IEEE Transactions on industrial electronics*, 56(12), 4744-4756.

de la Torre, L., Sanchez, J., Dormido, S., Sánchez, J. P., Yuste, M., & Carreras, C. (2011). Two web-based laboratories of the FisL@ bs network: Hooke's and Snell's laws. *European Journal of Physics*, 32(2), 571.

Potkonjak, V., Vukobratović, M., Jovanović, K., & Medenica, M. (2010). Virtual Mechatronic/Robotic laboratory—A step further in distance learning. *Computers & Education*, 55(2), 465-475.

Osentoski, S., Pitzer, B., Crick, C., Jay, G., Dong, S., Grollman, D., ... & Jenkins, O. C. (2012). Remote Robotic Laboratories for Learning from Demonstration: Enabling user interaction and shared experimentation. *International Journal of Social Robotics*, 4, 449-461.

Argall, B. D., Chernova, S., Veloso, M., & Browning, B. (2009). A survey of robot learning from demonstration. *Robotics and autonomous systems*, 57(5), 469-483.

Dillmann, R. (1995). Robot Programming by Demonstration. *Proc. 7th ISRR*, 249-258.

Wolf, Á., Wolton, D., Trapl, J., Janda, J., Romeder-Finger, S., Gatternig, T., ... & Széll, K. (2022). Towards robotic laboratory automation Plug & Play: The “LAPP” framework. *SLAS technology*, 27(1), 18-25.

Grosz, E. A., & Borzan, M. (2025). Modular Robotics Configurator: A MATLAB Model-Based Development Approach. *Applied System Innovation*, 8(1), 21.

Jia, J., & Sun, X. (2023). Structural Optimization Design of a Six-Degrees-of-Freedom Serial Robot with Integrated Topology and Dimensional Parameters. *Sensors*, 23(16), 7183.

Tsai, C. H., Hernandez, E. E., You, X. W., Lin, H. Y., & Chang, J. Y. (2023). RoboTwin Metaverse

Platform for Robotic Random Bin Picking. *Applied Sciences*, 13(15), 8779.

Grosz, E. A., Lapusan, C., & Brisan, C. (2020, December). Aspects regarding the development of a gripper with variable geometry. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* (Vol. 997, No. 1, p. 012076). IOP Publishing.

Karupusamy, S., Maruthachalam, S., & Veerasamy, B. (2024). Kinematic Modeling and Performance Analysis of a 5-DoF Robot for Welding Applications. *Machines*, 12(6), 378.

Toledano-García, A. A., Pérez-Cabrera, H. R., Ortega-Cabrera, D., Navarro-Durán, D., & Pérez-Hernández, E. M. (2023). Trajectory Generator System for a UR5 Collaborative Robot in 2D and 3D Surfaces. *Machines*, 11(9), 916.

De Backer, K., & DeStefano, T. (2021). Robotics and the global organisation of production. *Robotics, AI, and Humanity: Science, Ethics, and Policy*, 71-84.